

The Determinants and Consequences of Smoking Trends Among the Youths of Balochistan

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Abstract

Smoking is indeed the first ladder that elevates youth to the culmination of heavy drugs. The purpose of this paper is to examine the understanding of youth about the smoking orientation; the factors which are promoting smoking trends and the consequences of the smoking behavior. The study was carried out on the positivist approach of quantitative research study, where the data was collected from youth of Balochistan about the smoking trends. The data was gathered through simple random sampling technique from the sample size of 200 individuals/respondents. The findings outlined the company or the peer groups and the inadequate parental supervision are the major reasons turning the youth to smoking behavior; besides this the study found that e-cigarette and different flavors in e-cigarette have accelerated the trend among the youth. Moreover, the study resulted that the smoking habit is causing health issues and familial and social stigma. The study suggests that smoking is a harmful risk factor subverting the most crucial segment of the society. The government should revisit the tobacco controlling policies, intervene to restrict perceived accessibility to cigarette and take all possible measure to discourage smoking.

Keywords: Smoking, Cigarette, Trends, Youth, Determinants, Consequences

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